
PR (PUBLIC RELATIONS) TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF DOMESTIC TOURISM IN THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN.

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Abstract

The article discusses the issues of improving the organizational, economic and institutional mechanisms for managing the tourism industry in Uzbekistan. The author concluded that the tourist services market is constantly expanding in all countries of the world, and that the Republic of Uzbekistan, as compared with other countries, is characterized by specific features of the tourist potential.

Key words

tourism, services, management, management, marketing, profit, tourist

Introduction.

In the transition to an innovative economy, the tourism industry is becoming one of the most promising areas. In many countries, the turnover of the tourism industry is tens of percent of GDP. Thus, according to the materials of the International Tourism Organization [8], the share of tourism in world GDP is about 9 percent and about 30 percent in world exports of services, 6 percent of world trade. More than 235 million people, or every 12 employees, work in the field of tourism. According to the World Tourism and Travel Council, the indirect income of the tourism industry in 2016 was 3 trillion. US dollars [9], and mediated income amounted to 22,800 billion US dollars. The number of workers in the region exceeded 260 million people. It should also be said that over the past 20 years, tourist flows in the world have grown almost 2.2 times, from 435 million people in 1990 to 675 million people in 2000 and 940 people in 2010. In 2014, according to the World Tourism Organization, more than a trillion people traveled around the world. According to the forecasts of this organization, by 2020 the number of international tourist arrivals will exceed 1.5 billion, and revenues will increase to 2 trillion. USD. Below are data on the contribution of tourism to the GDP and employment of individual countries in 2016.

The role of cross-border free economic zones in improving economic geographical and regional trade and economic relations has been widely and

effectively studied by foreign scientists. One of such scientists was G.M. In costume. In his article (Kostyunina&Baronov, 2011) investigated the activities of transborderFEZs on the example of Hexhe, Suffenheim, Manchuria and Hunchun on the Russian-Chinese border. The main problems in the development of these areas are the transport and logistics system and high land rent. Indeed, the problem of transport and logistics at cross-border FEZs is one of the main issues of all cross-border EEs not only on the China-Russia border but in the world economy. According to a study by the Thai Mekong Institute (Dutta et al,2018), it is possible to increase transport capacity and develop entrepreneurship by establishing a transborder FEA within the Mekong River Basin countries. P.V. Pavlov according to a study by (Pavlov, 2006), free economic zones have been proven to be an important element in enhancing Russia's role in international economic integration processes, and, according to the author's typology of free economic zones, transborder free economic zones are also listed as a type of special FEZ. Many studies and analyzes (Masami, 2009) show that transborderFEZs are not only border areas, but also the similarity of the foreign economic and political objectives of neighboring countries, the level of living within a single group, the size of GDP, and the accessibility of countries to the sea.

Accordingly, increased attention to tourism from world organizations. The leaders of the G20 countries in a declaration following the annual meeting in 2014 recognized "the importance of the travel and tourism industry as a means of creating jobs, ensuring economic growth and development" and committed themselves "to develop initiatives to facilitate travel, which will help create jobs, ensuring decent work, reducing poverty and ensuring global economic growth "[10]. As world experience shows, to achieve economic growth, one of the promising areas is the effective use of the competitive advantages of the tourism sector. In this regard, Uzbekistan pays close attention to the development of the tourism sector, since in many regions there are favorable conditions for the development of this industry. Thus, in the main government document "Strategy of Action" [4], adopted at the initiative of President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, one of the main priorities was the accelerated development of the tourism industry, increasing its role and contribution to the economy, diversification and improvement of the quality of tourist services, expansion of tourist infrastructure.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The work of V.I. Azara, M.A. Ananeva, E.I. Ilina, G.A. Karpovoy, A.T. Kirillova, R. Yu. Popova, V.B. Saprunova, B.C. Seiina and other scientists. Regional

aspects of tourism were considered in the works of V.G. Bogdanova, B.M. Birzhakova, L.A. Volkova et al. Basic research in the field of tourism management is reflected in the works of P.A. Braimera, E.I. Voronova, I.I.I. Kabushkina, V.A. Kvartalnova. Among the foreign experts working in this direction, we can mention P. Buckley, M. Brucke, R. Grande, D. Jeffreys, J. Kripendorff, and others. There were several researches in field of effectively usage of industry potential by scientists as well as Zubarevich N.[10-11], Kazantsev S.V., Merenkova I.N., Nosov A.K., Pantelev A.P., Sepik D., Serebryakova L.A., Gulyamov S.S., Sadykov A.M., B. Ruzmetov, [12-13], research works about textile development in Uzbekistan investigated by young economists as Hakimov Z. and Tursunov B. [14-20]. Analysis of the works of these and other authors shows that by now certain prerequisites have been created, a range of basic organizational and economic ideas, provisions and approaches have been formed to improve the theory and practice of tourism management.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY The methods of scientific abstraction, induction, deduction, analysis and synthesis were effectively used during the study. The results obtained through the economic-mathematical methods (Gravitational model) were used to draw general conclusions on the topic of scientific research. **FOREIGN EXPERIENCE** In the context of globalization, no country can develop in isolation and interdependence. In particular, Uzbekistan has been pursuing an active foreign economic policy since the first years of independence. Today Uzbekistan is a country with a relatively high growth rate, playing an important role in the system of international relations and being a member of the international community. His demographic and socio-economic reforms are being studied with great interest among world scientists as new models of development. Secretary of the European Economic Commission A. Vasilev argues that "Uzbekistan is an important country in the Central Asian region with a well-developed and diversified economy (Gazeta.uz, 2014). However, limited access to the sea and the diversity of economic and political conditions in neighboring countries, as well as the political situation in Afghanistan, are the major obstacles to foreign trade. One of the solutions to this problem is the expansion of regional economic relations with Kazakhstan. According to the authors, four of the major transport corridors in Uzbekistan's foreign trade pass through Kazakhstan, creating a free economic zone (FEZ) in the border areas of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan, considering the foreign trade issues. In world practice, transborder FEZs are common in the experience of the People's Republic of China,

China, Japan, the Republic of Korea and the European Union, Southeast Asia. In world practice, such FEZs have been used as the first stage of regional economic integration. The FEZ, despite its varied forms, has allowed to increase trade between countries and to diversify and stimulate production. Looking at the PRC experience, such zones have been established in China since 1992, and currently there are about 90 cross-border economic zones in the country. China's transborder free economic zones are located on the border of Japan and Russia (Hehehe, Suffenhe, Manchuria, Hunchun), the development of mutual trade between neighboring countries (border and territorial trade); diversification of industrial sectors; great opportunities for the development of small and medium-sized businesses (Kostyunina&Baronov,2011).

Another important alternative is the establishment of a transborderFEZ in the border areas of Uzbekistan in Andijan and in the Osh region of the Kyrgyz Republic. Andijan region has the following transport infrastructure: - The length of automobile roads is almost 2.5 thousand km; - Flights from Andijan region to all CIS countries; - Availability of railroads running from Andijan region to the Andijan-Tashkent, Andijan-Jalalabad / Osh and other local areas. The presence of large heavy and light industry enterprises in the Uzbek province of Andijan also facilitates the establishment of a transborder FEZ in the region. One of the border areas of Uzbekistan with Central Asia is the Khorezm region of Uzbekistan and Dashaguz provinces of Turkmenistan. During the visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan ShavkatMirziyoev to Turkmenistan, the governments of the border areas of the two countries, including Khorezm region and Dashoguz province of Turkmenistan, agreed on cooperation in trade, economic, cultural and humanitarian spheres. In particular, a system of participation in international fairs, exhibitions, seminars and conferences was planned to facilitate mutually beneficial cooperation between enterprises and organizations, the establishment of joint ventures and the joint use of the tourism potential of both regions (Bobojonov, 2017). In addition, Turkmenistan is a seaside country and the establishment of a trans-border FEZ at the time of the opening of the UzbekistanTurkmenistan-Iran-Oman transport corridor will improve trade and economic relations between Uzbekistan and not only Turkmenistan, but also Iran and the Persian Gulf. The major partners of Uzbekistan such as China and Russia are also interested in this agreement.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the study the author came to the following conclusion: 1) Transborder free economic zones are important for Central Asian countries, where trade and economic relations are developing. In particular, for Uzbekistan, which has limited access to the sea, such zones provide the following opportunities: - Transborder zone established on the border of Uzbekistan with Khorezm and Dashaguz provinces of Turkmenistan Uzbekistan improves access to sea, improves trade and economic relations with Forz Gulf through the transport corridor Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan-Iran-Oman and exports of consumer goods produced in Uzbekistan to the Turkmen market. capacity increases; - The establishment of cross-border FEZ in the border areas of Andijan and Osh regions of the Kyrgyz Republic is an alternative option for the joint textile and knitwear companies and their infrastructure, taking into account the entry of Kyrgyz goods into the European market for more than 6,000 commodity items. is considered - Creation of the Chirchik-Sariagash Transborder Free Economic Zone of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan will allow the development of trade and economic relations with China and Russia along with the effective use of four transport corridors of Uzbekistan. 2) However, the economic policy of the countries is also important in establishing such free economic zones. For example, given that Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan are members of the WTO and the Eurasian Economic Community, there is a risk that Uzbekistan's high-cost commodities will be less competitive and that food and machine industries in Uzbekistan will be at risk. 3) The creation of a transborder free economic zone in Central Asia is relevant until the economic integration of Central Asian countries is established.

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